

MEDICAL SCIENCES

АНАЛІЗ РІВНЯ СТРЕСУ У СТУДЕНТІВ ПІД ЧАС НАВЧАННЯ В УМОВАХ ВОЄННОГО СТАНУ

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ANALYZING THE LEVEL OF STRESS IN STUDENTS WHILE STUDYING UNDER MARTIAL LAW

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Анотація

У статті проаналізовано вплив стресу на студентів різних навчальних закладів в умовах війни. За даними статистичного дослідження було виявлено, що всі опитані відчують стрес під час навчання у більшій або меншій мірі. У третини стрес навіть перетворився на хронічний.

Abstract

The article analyses the impact of stress on students of different educational institutions in the context of war. According to the statistical study, it was found that all respondents experience stress during their studies to a greater or lesser extent. For one third, stress has even become chronic.

Ключові слова: Стрес, вища освіта, стрес під час навчання, стресостійкість, психологічна підтримка, методи подолання стресу, навчання під час війни.

Keywords: Stress, higher education, stress during studying, stress resistance, psychological support, methods of overcoming stress, studying during war.

During their studies, students are strongly influenced by various stress factors, especially during the exam period. The stress experienced by students is characterized as chronic. There is an acute form of stress - "exam stress". Among the factors that influence the formation of this condition are the following: an increase in intellectual workload, emotional experiences due to the results of tests and exams, changes in rest and sleep patterns, lack of time for preparation, a tight schedule of tests and exams, high levels of anxiety, etc. The body's response to stress can be active or passive. There are usually three stages of stress response development:

1) anxiety stage - manifested in increased personal control of the situation, concentration of attention on the stimulus;

2) the stage of resistance - mental and physical activity is aimed at coping with a stressful situation;

3) the stage of exhaustion - if the stimulus is prolonged, a feeling of anxiety reappears, and the body is exhausted [1,2].

The war has had a significant impact on the mental state of students. In addition to the problems that arise during their studies, they also have to deal with worries about their lives and the lives of their loved ones. The psychosocial impact on students in conflict zones is profound and often leads to a number of mental health

disorders, including post-traumatic stress disorder, depression, and anxiety. The topic of mental health and ways to improve it among students is relevant and important, as it has been found that many students experience a wide range of negative emotional states, with apathy leading the list, which affects the quality of life and education of young people [3,7]. This has a serious impact on the assimilation of information. For example: reduced motivation, impaired memory and concentration, impaired ability to perceive and think, etc. The form of education has a great impact on the level of stress. It should be noted that students experience stress in distance learning in a similar way to full-time education. According to statistics, the transition to full-time education has had a worse impact on student performance [5].

Data from medical and psychological studies indicate a fairly high incidence of diseases of "stress etiology" among students. The period of studying at higher education institution coincides with the age when there is a high risk of developing mental disorders due to significant stressful loads. According to research, the risk of mental illness among students is highest in the junior year. This is due to difficulties in adapting to new professional and living conditions. After the 3rd year of study, the risk decreases, being minimal in the 4th-6th years of study [6].

The period of study has a significant impact on the formation of personality, so the problem of students' mental health is very relevant. Stress in the learning process needs to be regulated. This should be done by both students and higher education institutions [8].

Among the individual factors of successful socio-psychological adaptation of students of higher education institutions, an important role belongs to the level of stress resistance of the individual, its high level contributes to the preservation of physical and mental health of students in overcoming stressful situations at the beginning of their studies and further professional activities [9].

According to scientific and practical research, higher education institutions should conduct interviews for students of all years of study, research based on psychodiagnostic methods to identify negative mental states, organize and conduct trainings for successful social and psychological adaptation [10].

Based on scientific sources, it can be concluded that psychological support is very important for students, as they not only suffer from current circumstances but also face an uncertain future [11].

Identification of a group of students who have lost motivation to study and are disappointed in their decision should encourage educational institutions to take measures, such as developing recommendations and methods to improve the psycho-emotional state of students in order to correct possible negative influences and changes in professional orientations in the future. A comprehensive approach by a higher education institution may include: organizing events in schools to introduce future specialties; promoting personal and conscious choice of profession and the inadmissibility of pressure from the environment; improving curricula and creating a friendly academic environment; monitoring the psychological state of students [12].

To determine the impact of stress on students during studying and examination sessions. To determine the process of stress formation and the factors that influence it. To investigate how the health status of the respondents and their relationships with loved ones changed during their studies. To develop measures to

combat stress on the part of students and higher education institutions.

To conduct the study, an online questionnaire was created using Google Forms and distributed to students of various higher education institutions. The survey involved 297 respondents aged 16-34 years (mean age 19 ± 1.9 years), mostly students of 1-4 years of study. Among them, 29% (86 people) were men and 71% (211 people) were women.

At the beginning, the respondents were asked to define their level of stress using a scale from 1-10. Subsequently, all students were divided into groups according to their level of stress (1-4 – low, 5-7 – medium, 8-10 – high). Evaluating the data obtained, it was found that 44% of respondents experience a high level of stress, 43% – medium and 13% – low.

In the next section, a study was conducted to identify the causes of stress. The respondents were offered five options (reasons) with the following results: academic performance rating – 60% (177 people), pressure from teachers – 43% (129 people), lack of literature – 26% (77 people), heavy workload during studies – 88% (262 people), fear of the future – 56% (167 people). The most significant stress factor was excessive workload, which may be due to the intensity of the educational program and the need to master a large amount of material in a short time. The least significant reason was the lack of literature, which is likely to be due to the widespread access to information through digital sources, including artificial intelligence and online services.

The next question was about determining the acute level of stress during the exam session. It was found that 64% (190 people) of respondents experience a significant negative impact, 30% (89 people) – a minor one, while 6% (18 people) do not experience stress at all. The gender analysis revealed that among women, 69% (145 people) experience a high level of stress, 26% (55 people) – a moderate level, and 5% (11 people) – no impact. Among men, 53% (46 people) reported a high level of stress, 38% (32 people) – a moderate level, and only 9% (8 people) did not experience stress during the session (Fig. 1).

Figure. 1: The impact of stress during the exam session

The respondents were asked to identify how their condition worsened under the study time and sessions. Ten answer options were provided for this purpose. The results were as follows: poor sleep – 76% (225 people), nervous breakdowns and conflicts with loved ones – 48% (143 people), headaches or chest discomfort – 56% (165 people), digestive problems - 38% (114 people), reduced concentration – 59% (175 people), low level of performance and fatigue – 67% (200 people), rushing and feeling of constant lack of time – 69% (206 people), frustration and self-doubt – 56% (166 people),

desire to change profession – 33% 98 (people), desire to change educational institution – 29% (87 people).

In the section on assessing the emotional state of students, the range of emotions that arise in the learning process was analyzed. The results showed that 86% (255 people) of the respondents feel anxiety, 58% (172 people) – apathy, 57% (169 people) – fear, 56% (165 people) – guilt, and 39% (116 people) – anger (Fig. 2). The data obtained indicate a high level of emotional stress among students.

Figure. 2: Emotions experienced by students during the training

An important issue in the study was the impact of the war on the educational process and the mental state

of students. 62% (184 people) of the respondents said that the war had a significant impact on them, while

38% (113 people) did not. Next, it was revealed what kind of impact students are exposed to. The most common responses were: fear for life, air raids and loud explosions, and lack of sleep.

As the form of education is unstable due to the hostilities, respondents were given the opportunity to express their opinion on distance and on-site learning. The survey showed that 44% (131 people) do not feel stress during distance learning, while 36% (107 people) felt such an impact, and only 20% (59 people) were undecided. Only 41% (122 people) were positive, justifying their opinion with the fact that it is better to be in society, many new opportunities open up and there is live communication, which is much more useful. 59% responded negatively, citing the stress of waking up early, overcoming the long commute to and from university, lack of sleep, irritability, panic and frustration.

It was also important to determine how the respondents' relationships with their family and friends had deteriorated during their studies. The largest number of respondents, 64% (189 people), said they had started to communicate less with their loved ones, 32% (96 people) felt irritated by their advice, 21% (63 people) said they were constantly snapping at their relatives and had difficulty accepting their support. And only 4% (13 people) of respondents did not feel that their relationships with their loved ones had deteriorated.

The last section of the study was devoted to the development of stress management techniques. Here, respondents shared their methods of coping with stress and provided recommendations for students and higher education institutions.

Among their own ways of coping with stress, the survey participants mentioned the following: exercise, spending more time outdoors, communicating with friends and family, and distracting themselves with a favorite hobby.

Among the recommendations given by respondents on measures that should be taken by an educational institution to improve the mental state of students, the most common were: even distribution of the workload on students, free psychological training, creation of a convenient schedule, even workload and interesting entertainment events.

Having analyzed the results of the study, we can conclude that stress is a constant companion of students during their studies. It is necessary to pay attention to the psychological state of students not only during the session, but also in the period between exams, as it is very disturbing and exhausting. According to the survey, it was noted that students experience stress equally in both full-time and distance learning. It should be borne in mind that the hostilities have had a significant impact on higher education students. According to the survey, students report a deterioration in their ability to concentrate and learn, which has led to a decline in academic performance. In this regard, it is important to implement effective measures to reduce stress levels, which will improve both the psycho-emotional state of students and their academic achievements. This task re-

quires joint efforts of both students and the administration of higher education institutions to create a favorable educational environment.

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